

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

PLANNING STRATEGIC CHANGES IN AN ENTERPRISE AMID UNCERTAINTY: STRATEGIC AND OPERATIONAL ASPECTS

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Abstract

Provisions for ensuring the substantive transformation of the strategic change planning paradigm—shifting from the use of rigid algorithms to the formation of flexible adaptation systems—are substantiated. It is established that under conditions of critical turbulence, traditional methods of extrapolating past experience lose their effectiveness, giving way to dynamic capabilities. The expediency of transitioning from deterministic models to stochastic approaches, where each decision is considered through the prism of alternative scenarios, is proven. The priority of using enterprise resilience and antifragility indicators within the planning system for dynamic changes across strategic and operational aspects is established. The expediency of implementing real-time feedback mechanisms for the automatic correction of strategic priorities is proven. The role of the ethical dimension and reputational capital as stabilizing factors during periods of chaotic environmental changes is substantiated.

Keywords: planning, planning activity, dynamic changes, enterprise strategy, operational planning, strategic planning, uncertainty, risks.

Introduction. In the field of strategic change planning at enterprises under modern conditions, a substantive transformation is occurring, whereby the use of fixed and repetitive action algorithms in the planning process is gradually being replaced by the formation of a flexible system of adaptation to critical environmental uncertainty. In the current economic situation, where the application of traditional methods of extrapolating past experience in preparing planning decisions fundamentally loses effectiveness, the support of strategic orientation in planning increasingly focuses on implementing principles of ensuring dynamic development capabilities and multi-alternative scenario modeling.

Therefore, the actual nature of implementing strategic changes under such circumstances is revealed not so much through changes in the organizational structure or the business product portfolio composition, but through the creation of mechanisms for accelerated and flexible response to poorly predictable or unpredictable challenges. This allows business entities to maintain viability and competitive advantages even under conditions of partial loss of resources or markets, disruption of logistics chains, or radical changes in market conditions, etc.

The use of such teleological planning concepts acquires particular relevance for Ukrainian enterprises both in the current context of a leap-like increase in risks and threats to activities related to economic choice limitations under martial law, and in the prospect of growing competition during the future post-war revival of the national economy.

Analysis of recent research and publications.

The methodological basis of planning activities under uncertainty lies in the expanded use (unlike the more

traditional use of deterministic models) of stochastic approaches, where each strategic decision is considered through the prism of alternative development scenarios. The implementation of such an approach implies the need for deep analysis not only of existing trends and identified tendencies but also for predicting the consequences of the impact of factors whose changes are marked by weak signals that may indicate the approach of bifurcation points in the economic system and economic environment.

The conceptual foundation for planning strategic changes at an enterprise under conditions of uncertainty was formed and carefully studied in the works of many prominent scholars, such as Anderson C. [1], Bernard S. [2], Brocke J. [3], Dicken P. [41], Dietz J. [5], Fortino A. [6], Gligorevic J. [11], Grefen P. [8], Janssen T. [7], Kassapian F. [11], Kern J. [10], McGroarty F. [12], Mehandjiev N. [8], Mendling J. [3], Mulder H. [5], Shmatko N. [9], Sullivan M. [10], Wilde D. [11], Ziouvelou X. [12], etc. On the other hand, the problems of developing modern scenario planning methods based on accounting for multi-alternative development perspectives remain insufficiently researched and require further detailed consideration to this day.

The aim of the research in this work is to substantiate the theoretical and methodological provisions regarding the planning of dynamic changes at an enterprise under conditions of increasing uncertainty in the economic environment.

Research Results. The effective execution of the strategic change planning process requires a fundamental revision of traditional time horizons for management decision-making. Under conditions of high uncertainty, the traditional long-term vision of development

prospects must be continuously combined with extremely short operational planning iterations. The necessity of such a combination is determined by the requirements of implementing agile management methods at the highest level of strategic management, which allows for continuous monitoring, verification, control, and adjustment of goals and tools for their achievement.

The central place in the structure of the planning process built in this way is occupied by the continuous assessment of the enterprise's resource potential, with a particular emphasis on the liquidity and functional mobility of the business entity's assets. Consequently, the success of achieving set goals, considering the probability of identifying risks of various transformations in a turbulent environment, directly depends on the organization's ability to rapidly redistribute financial, human, and intellectual assets among different vectors of activity, while minimizing transaction costs and time for business process reformatting.

The effectiveness of strategic change planning in a turbulent environment can no longer be adequately assessed using standard indicators of profitability or market share in the short term. Assessment priorities in this context inevitably shift toward identifying integrated indicators of resilience (systemic stability that defines capabilities for maintaining operational stability and ensuring post-crisis recovery) and antifragility (the ability to withstand entropic tendencies) of the enterprise.

The concept of antifragility, in turn, envisages the formation of the enterprise's ability not only to simply restore its previous state after external shocks but also to strengthen potential and increase operational efficiency by overcoming crisis situations. The mechanism for monitoring the implementation of changes must be built on the principle of real-time feedback. Any minimal deviation from the expected parameters of the external or internal environment should automatically initiate a procedure for revising strategic priorities, giving the enterprise the traits of a living organism that constantly learns and evolves. Thus, strategic change planning under uncertainty transforms into a permanent process of organizational learning, where the main output of management activity is not a static document with an action plan, but a developed ability to quickly orient oneself in information chaos and make high-quality management decisions under conditions of incomplete or contradictory information.

The methodological foundation of planning under uncertainty thus requires the involvement of game theory and systems analysis to build models of interaction with competitors and state regulators. In a situation where the external environment is characterized by features of chaos, strategic planning takes on the traits of designing the future rather than simply following circumstances. This means that in its plans, the enterprise must envision an active influence on the environment through the formation of new standards, development of cooperative links, and creation of ecosystems. Such an expanded understanding of strategy allows for reducing the level of external uncertainty by creating a

stabilizing field of loyal partners, clients, and consumers around the enterprise. Within this process, strategic planning acts as a tool for synchronizing internal organizational rhythms with the dynamics of global markets, requiring a high level of cognitive flexibility from the management.

Special attention during strategic change planning should be paid to the decision-making architecture, which must be decentralized and multi-level. Under modern conditions of sequential reduction in the time for making anti-crisis decisions, the classical rigid hierarchy becomes a barrier that delays necessary transformations. Therefore, the strategic plan should provide for the transfer of significant powers to the level of line managers who are in direct contact with market realities. Such decentralization does not imply a loss of control but, conversely, is based on a high level of trust and unity of value orientations fixed in the strategy. These changes allow the enterprise to ensure a collective nature of personnel involvement in management, whereby decision-making at different management levels is aligned with the understanding of the general direction of movement while maintaining flexibility of response to achieve local results.

A separate critically important element of the planning mechanism in this context is the consideration of the psychological factor and resistance to change, which significantly increases under conditions of general instability due to the high stress levels of personnel. Consequently, the strategic plan must contain an extensive communication system and measures to increase the adaptability of the corporate culture, which turns employees into active participants in transformation processes. Planning in such conditions becomes an inclusive process where lower management levels are involved in identifying risks and opportunities, ensuring greater accuracy of forecasts and speed of implementation of planned measures.

An important economic aspect of planning activity under this approach is also the integration of intellectual capital management mechanisms (primarily actions for forming dynamic business competencies) into the strategic planning system. Under uncertainty, knowledge and unique personnel competencies become the most stable asset that does not lose its value when economic paradigms change. Planning for changes should include continuous training and retraining programs, ensuring the readiness of employees to perform new functional duties within the updated strategy. This allows for avoiding crisis situations related to a deficit of competencies during radical changes in technological processes or entry into new markets. Thus, strategic planning takes on the traits of human-centeredness, where the development of an employee's personal potential is viewed as a guarantee of the strategic stability of the entire system.

Within the functional support of strategic change planning, it is necessary to consider the institutional aspects of market operation. This includes the analysis of regulatory risks, changes in legislation, and tax policy, which can occur quite unpredictably under conditions of instability. The strategic plan must contain blocks of adaptation to legal changes, allowing the enterprise to

remain within the legal field while minimizing administrative pressure and legal risks. The ability for rapid legal and commercial reformatting of contractual relationships with partners is a significant advantage that should be embedded in the planning methodology as one of the key operational options.

The final stage of the planning system transformation is the transition to the concept of continuous strategizing. These conceptual changes envisage that the strategy development process does not end with the approval of a specific document but continues daily in the form of monitoring, reflection, and adjustment. Such an approach requires management to form a specific analytical mindset capable of synthesizing large arrays of disparate data into a coherent picture of the strategic landscape. Planning under uncertainty becomes the highest manifestation of managerial art, where scientific calculation is combined with intuition and the capacity for risk. Ultimately, the quality of strategic planning determines whether an enterprise will become a victim of circumstances or be able to use the chaos of the external environment as fuel for its own innovative development and long-term prosperity.

Analyzing organizational structures that adapt best to change, the expediency of transitioning from functional specialization to cross-functional teams should be noted. In the strategic planning process, such teams should be formed for specific strategic initiatives, bringing together specialists in finance, marketing, production, and logistics. This avoids fragmentation of vision and ensures an integrated approach to solving complex problems. The coordination of such groups should occur on the basis of partnership rather than dictates, which significantly speeds up the exchange of ideas and decision-making. Thus, strategic change planning acts as a catalyst for internal organizational transformations aimed at creating a more horizontal and democratic management structure capable of self-organization at critical moments.

The ethical dimension of strategic planning under crisis conditions also acquires special significance. Corporate social responsibility toward employees, the community, and the state should not be a mere formal declaration but an organic part of the strategic plan. Under uncertainty, trust and reputation become those intangible assets that help attract resources and support during the most difficult times. Therefore, planning for changes must consider the long-term interests of all stakeholders, providing the enterprise with a high level of social legitimacy and support. This creates an additional margin of safety, which often proves to be a decisive factor in the struggle for market leadership.

Conclusions. As a result of the conducted research, it is substantiated that strategic change planning at a modern enterprise undergoes a fundamental paradigmatic transformation, turning from a process of developing static algorithms into a flexible adaptation system to critical uncertainty. It is established that under conditions where traditional extrapolation of past experience loses relevance, the methodological basis of planning must shift toward stochastic approaches and multi-alternative scenario modeling.

The effectiveness of strategizing in a turbulent environment depends on management's ability to combine long-term vision with extremely short operational planning iterations. The key factor for success in this context is not simply the availability of resources but their liquidity and functional mobility, allowing for the rapid redistribution of capital and competencies among various vectors of activity. Priorities for assessing the effectiveness of changes inevitably shift from short-term profitability to integrated indicators of resilience and antifragility, which determine an enterprise's ability not only to recover after shocks but also to strengthen its potential by overcoming crises.

In this context, special significance is acquired by the decision-making architecture, which must transform from a rigid hierarchy into decentralized cross-functional teams. Such an approach stimulates planning inclusivity, where involving personnel in risk identification allows for neutralizing psychological resistance and high stress levels. Under uncertainty, strategic planning takes on traits of human-centeredness, where intellectual capital management and the development of dynamic competencies become the main guarantee of system stability.

Directions for further research in this field will be related to examining the prospects for the digitalization of management processes when planning strategic changes.

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